

Research Article

Development and Evaluation of Emulgel Loaded with *Pongamia pinnata* Seed Oil and *Wrightia tinctoria* Leaf Extract for the Treatment of Skin Disorders

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ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to develop and evaluate an emulgel loaded with *Pongamia pinnata* seed oil and *Wrightia tinctoria* leaf extract for the treatment of skin disorders, with a particular focus on antimicrobial activity. *Pongamia pinnata* seed oil was extracted by mechanical pressing, while *Wrightia tinctoria* leaves were subjected to hot aqueous extraction. Four O/W type emulgel formulations (F1–F4) were prepared by incorporating a herbal emulsion into a gel base and evaluated for their physicochemical properties. All formulations exhibited good appearance, suitable pH, spreadability, extrudability, and stability without phase separation, with F4 showing the most favorable characteristics. Antimicrobial studies revealed that *Wrightia tinctoria* leaf extract showed strong antifungal activity with a MIC of 25 µl/ml against *Candida albicans*. In comparison, *Pongamia pinnata* seed oil and its combination showed moderate inhibition at 50 µl/ml. Against *Staphylococcus aureus*, both extracts were effective at 50 µl/ml, whereas the mixture showed reduced efficacy (MIC 100 µl/ml). The results suggest that topical emulgel formulations containing these extracts may offer dual antifungal and antibacterial effects, though further in vivo and extended antimicrobial studies are warranted to confirm therapeutic potential.

INTRODUCTION

Skin disorders such as eczema, psoriasis, and dermatitis are common inflammatory conditions often requiring long-term management. Herbal drugs offer safe and effective alternatives, with

Pongamia pinnata seed oil known for its anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and wound-healing properties, and *Wrightia tinctoria* traditionally used for treating psoriasis and other dermal ailments. However, conventional formulations

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face limitations in terms of penetration and stability.¹

Pongamia pinnata seeds yield oil rich in bioactive compounds such as karanjin, pongamol, oleic acid, and linoleic acid, which exhibit diverse pharmacological properties including antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities.² Similarly, *Wrightia tinctoria* contains flavonoids, triterpenoids, and glycosides, which contribute to its therapeutic efficacy in treating skin diseases. To overcome formulation challenges and enhance delivery, emulgel serves as an effective drug carrier system by combining the advantages of emulsions and gels, offering improved Spreadability, stability, and controlled release³

An emulgel is a dual-acting topical formulation in which an emulsion (O/W or W/O) is incorporated into a gel base using gelling agents such as Carbopol or HPMC. This system enables the delivery of both lipophilic and hydrophilic drugs, provides thermodynamic stability, reduces interfacial tension, and ensures controlled release of active ingredients through both emulsion and gel phases. Additionally, emulgel offer improved

Spreadability, non-greasy texture, and patient compliance, making them highly suitable for dermatological applications.^{4, 5} Therefore, the present study aims to develop and evaluate an herbal emulgel containing *Pongamia pinnata* seed oil and *Wrightia tinctoria* leaf extract for the treatment of skin disorders, with emphasis on antimicrobial activity, stability, and therapeutic potential.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Collection and Authentication:

The seeds of *Pongamia pinnata* were collected from Tukkanatti, Belagavi district, Karnataka, India, while the leaves of *Wrightia tinctoria* were obtained from the medicinal garden of Rani Chennamma College of Pharmacy, Belagavi, Karnataka, India. The plant materials were authenticated by the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) – National Institute of Traditional Medicine (NITM), Karnataka, India, and accession number of specimens were retained for future reference.

Pongamia pinnata

Wrightia tinctoria

Figure 1: Authentication letter

Method of Preparation of Plant Extracts:^{6, 7}

***Wrightia tinctoria* leaf extract:** Healthy leaves of *Wrightia tinctoria* were collected and shade-dried

at room temperature to prevent degradation of bioactive constituents. The dried leaves were then powdered using a mixer, sieved to obtain uniform particle size, and stored in a well-closed container

in a dry place until use. A hot aqueous extract was prepared by mixing 10 g of the leaf powder with 100 mL of distilled water (10% w/v) and maintaining the mixture at a constant temperature of 60 °C. The extract was then filtered through Whatman filter paper to obtain a clear solution for further use.

Pongamia pinnata seed oil: Mature seeds of *Pongamia pinnata* were collected and thoroughly cleaned to remove dust, debris, and damaged seeds. The seeds were shade-dried (or sun-dried if necessary) to reduce moisture content. Further drying was performed, if required, to achieve an optimal moisture content of approximately 8–10%, which is ideal for efficient oil extraction. The dried kernels were then ground into a coarse powder or crushed to increase the surface area, thereby enhancing the extraction efficiency of the oil.

Figure 2: Extraction Process

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening of plant extracts:^{8, 11}

Hot aqueous extract of *Wrightia tinctoria* leaves was subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening to detect the presence of various classes of phytoconstituents, including alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, glycosides, and phenolic compounds, following standard qualitative procedures. The extracted oil from

Pongamia pinnata seeds was similarly analyzed for the presence of phytoconstituents such as fatty acids, flavonoids, phenolic, terpenoids, and other bioactive compounds using standard phytochemical screening methods as given in table 1 and 2.

Table 1. Phytochemical Screening of *Wrightia tinctoria* Leaf Extract

Phytochemical constituent	test	Inference
Flavonoids	Shinoda test	++
Alkaloids	Hager's test	+++
	Wagner's test	+++
Tannins	Ferric Chloride Test	++
	Lead Acetate	++

Phytochemical screening of *Wrightia tinctoria* leaf extract. The intensity of phytoconstituents is expressed as (+++) highly present, (++) moderately present

Table 2: Phytochemical screening of *Pongamia pinnata* seed oil

Phytochemical constituent	Test	Inference
Alkaloids	Wagner's test	+++
Steroids	Liebermann–Burchard test	++
Tannins and Phenolics	Ferric chloride test	++
Fixed oil and fats	Spot test	+++
Flavonoids	Shinoda test	+++

Phytochemical screening of *Pongamia pinnata* seed oil. The intensity of phytoconstituents is expressed as (+++) highly present, (++) moderately present

Preparation of Emulgel loaded with *Pongamia pinnata* seed oil and *Wrightia tinctoria* leaf extract: The emulgel formulation was prepared using a two-phase system: an aqueous phase and an oil phase. The aqueous phase consisted of Carbopol 934, methyl paraben, and distilled water. Oil phase: Contained *Pongamia pinnata* seed oil, *Wrightia tinctoria* leaf extract, liquid paraffin, and

isopropyl myristate. The aqueous and oil phases were separately prepared and then mixed. Triethanolamine was added to the mixture to neutralize Carbopol 934, resulting in the formation of a stable gel base.¹²⁻¹⁴

Table 3: Formulation of Emulgel loaded with plant extracts

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4
<i>Wrightia tinctoria</i> extract (ml)	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
<i>Pongamia pinnata</i> seed oil (ml)	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
Carbopol 934 (gm)	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Span 20 (ml)	1.75	1.75	1.75	1.75
Tween 80 (ml)	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75
Propylene glycol (ml)	5.0	5.0	---	---
PEG 400 (ml)	---	---	5.0	5.0
Methyl paraben (ml)	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Distilled water (q.s. to 50gm)	q.s.	q.s.	q.s.	q.s.

Formulation composition of emulgels (F1–F4) loaded with *Wrightia tinctoria* leaf extract and *Pongamia pinnata* seed oil. Propylene glycol

serves as a co-solvent in F1 and F2, while PEG 400 is incorporated in F3 and F4. Distilled water is added q.s. to make up the final weight to 50 g.

Figure 3: Prepared formulation of Emulgel loaded with plant extracts (F1- F4)

Evaluation of Emulgel: ^{15- 19}

Physical Appearance: The prepared emulgel formulations were inspected visually for color, consistency, and overall appearance.

Determination of pH: pH is a critical parameter for topical formulations to ensure compatibility with skin, which typically has a pH in the range of 5–7. A formulation with pH values outside this range may irritate. For evaluation, 1 g of the emulgel was dispersed in 100 mL of distilled water and allowed to stand for 2 hours. Measurements were carried out in triplicate using a calibrated pH meter and average values were recorded.

Spreadability: Spreadability determines the extent of area to which the emulgel spreads on application. A fixed amount of emulgel was placed between two glass slides (7.5 cm contact length). A 100 g weight was placed on the upper slide to allow uniform spreading, and excess gel was removed. The time taken by the upper slide to separate from the lower slide under a fixed weight was noted. The experiment was performed in triplicate, and the mean value was used for calculation.

The Spreadability was calculated using the formula:

$$S = \frac{M \times L}{T}$$

Where;

- S = Spreadability (g·cm/sec)
- M = Weight tied to upper slide (10 g)
- L = Length moved by the slide (6.8 cm)
- T = Time taken (sec)

Extrudability: Extrudability was determined as the force required to extrude the emulgel from a collapsible tube. The formulation was filled into lacquered aluminum collapsible tubes, and the amount of gel extruded was noted. A greater extruded quantity indicated better Extrudability. The Extrudability was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Extrudability (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weight extruded from tube (g)} \times 100}{\text{Total weight loaded in the tube (g)}}$$

Homogeneity: The prepared emulgel formulations were evaluated visually for uniformity by observing them against light. The formulations were checked for the presence of aggregates, lumps, coarse particles, or phase separation. A homogeneous emulgel was identified by its smooth texture and uniform appearance.

Stability Studies: Stability studies were carried out on the optimized emulgel formulation for a period of 30 days in accordance with ICH guidelines. The formulations were stored at 25 ± 1 °C and samples were withdrawn at 0, 15, and 30

days and evaluated for physical appearance, color, phase separation, pH, homogeneity and Spreadability. Any changes in these parameters were recorded to assess the physical and chemical stability of the formulation.

Antimicrobial Activity using Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC): The antimicrobial potential of the plant extracts in the emulgel was determined by MIC assay using Brain Heart Infusion (BHI) broth.

Procedure: Nine serial dilutions of each test sample were prepared. In the initial tube, 20 µL of extract was added to 380 µL of BHI broth. For subsequent dilutions, 200 µL of BHI broth was added into 9 test tubes separately. From the initial tube, 200 µL was transferred into the first tube containing 200 µL of BHI broth (10^{-1} dilution). From the 10^{-1} dilution, 200 µL was transferred into the second tube to make a 10^{-2} dilution, and the process was continued up to 10^{-9} dilution. From the stock culture of the required microorganisms, 5 µL was inoculated into 2 mL of BHI broth. In each serially diluted tube, 200 µL of the above culture suspension was added. The tubes were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours and observed for turbidity. The lowest concentration of extract that inhibited visible growth was considered as the MIC.^{20,21}

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 4. Results of prepared formulations

Sr. No.	Parameter	F1	F2	F3	F4
1.	Colour	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
2.	Appearance	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth
3.	pH	6.6	6.5	6.5	6.7
4.	Spreadability (g.cm/sec)	11.22	8.5	9.8	13.8
5.	Extrudability (%)	89.6	91.6	88.1	92.6
6.	Stability test	Found to be stable			

The results of the evaluation tests confirmed the stability and effectiveness of the developed

emulgel. All the formulations were evaluated for their Colour and appearance. The physical

appearances of all the formulations were found to be yellow in color, with a pleasant odor and smooth texture. The pH of all the formulations that is F1, F2, F3 and F4 were found to be in range of 6.5 to 6.7 which is good for skin pH. All the formulation of emulgel were shown pH nearer to skin required that is 5-7 pH. Spreadability study is one of the criteria for an emulgel to meet the ideal qualities that it should possess good Spreadability. If Spreadability value is more, it would be properly spread over the skin which is more beneficial as

per patient compliance concern. All the formulations were checked for the Spreadability and Extrudability. The data were given in the table 4. Among all the formulations, F4 showed better Spreadability and Extrudability. The antimicrobial activity of *Wrightia tinctoria* leaf extract, *Pongamia pinnata* seed oil, and their combination was evaluated against *Candida albicans* and *Staphylococcus aureus* using the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) method. The results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Antimicrobial activity of plant extracts by the MIC method

Sr. No.	Samples	100 µl/ml	50 µl/ml	25 µl/ml	12.5 µl/ml	6.25 µl/ml	3.12 µl/ml	1.6 µl/ml	0.8 µl/ml	0.4 µl/ml	0.2 µl/ml	B+C	B+O
	<i>Candida albicans</i>												
01	<i>Wrightia tinctoria</i>	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
02	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i>	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	S	R
03	Mixture	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
	<i>Staph aureus</i>												
01	<i>Wrightia tinctoria</i>	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
02	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i>	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
03	Mixture	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R

Antimicrobial activity of *Wrightia tinctoria* leaf extract, *Pongamia pinnata* seed oil, and their mixture against *Candida albicans* and *Staphylococcus aureus* at different concentrations.

“S” indicates sensitivity and “R” indicates resistance. B + C = Blank control, B + O = Blank ointment.

Table 6: MIC values of test samples against microorganisms

Sr. No.	Sample	MIC (µl/ml) – <i>Candida albicans</i>	MIC (µl/ml) – <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
01	<i>Wrightia tinctoria</i> leaf extract	25	50
02	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i> seed oil	50	50
03	Mixture (1:1)	50	100

The results indicate that *Wrightia tinctoria* leaf extract exhibited the highest antifungal activity with a MIC of 25 µl/ml against *Candida albicans*, while *Pongamia pinnata* seed oil and the mixture showed moderate inhibition at 50 µl/ml. Against

Staphylococcus aureus, both *Wrightia tinctoria* leaf extract and *Pongamia pinnata* seed oil were effective at 50 µl/ml, whereas the mixture showed a higher MIC of 100 µl/ml, suggesting reduced antibacterial efficacy in combination. Since

Wrightia tinctoria showed better antifungal activity and both extracts were moderately effective against *Staphylococcus aureus*, incorporating them into topical formulations such as gels or emulsions may provide dual action

against fungal and bacterial skin infections. Further evaluation through time-kill assays, zone of inhibition, and in vivo studies will be necessary to confirm their therapeutic relevance.

Figure 4: MIC dilution test of plant extracts against *E. coli* and *C. albicans*

CONCLUSION

The present study successfully developed and evaluated a stable and effective emulgel formulation incorporating *Pongamia pinnata* seed oil and *Wrightia tinctoria* leaf extract for potential topical application in the treatment of skin disorders. All prepared formulations (F1–F4) exhibited desirable physicochemical characteristics such as appropriate pH, smooth texture, good spreadability, and excellent extrudability without phase separation. Among them, formulation F4 demonstrated the most favorable performance in terms of spreadability and stability.

Phytochemical analysis confirmed the presence of bioactive constituents including flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, and fatty acids, which are responsible for the antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory activities of the extracts. Antimicrobial studies revealed that *Wrightia*

tinctoria exhibited strong antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* (MIC 25 μ l/ml), while *Pongamia pinnata* oil showed moderate antifungal and antibacterial activity. The combination of both extracts provided a balanced spectrum of antimicrobial effects, supporting their synergistic therapeutic potential.

Overall, the findings indicate that the developed herbal emulgel is a promising formulation for managing fungal and bacterial skin infections with good patient acceptability. Further *in vivo* studies and clinical evaluations are recommended to establish its safety, efficacy, and mechanism of action for potential pharmaceutical application.

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